

STEP 2 - paper screening

This survey will take you through some basic questions to (1) record basic info on the paper, (2) double check whether the paper fits the scope of the application review, and (3) to determine the number of applications described in the paper.

BASIC INFO: several verifiers will be extracted automatically, so less boring work for us. But we need to register a few aspects to be sure to couple the right papers and the right coders with the data.

SCOPE: a number of yes/no questions will need to be answered. if yes, the questionnaire continues. if no, we throw it out.

NUMBER of APPLICATIONS: if the paper is in scope, you will be asked to determine the number of valuation applications described in the paper.

Let's go!!

* Required

1. Email address *

Paper ID

double check
double double check

2. 0.1 - what's the paper ID *

3. 0.2 - what's the first authors' family name (to triple check) *

Empirical
paper?

Our review is based on actual valuations, performed in and actual real life setting. We want to remove papers which only theoretically discuss valuation. We will have pre-selected this as much as possible, but a double-check is required. Whether a paper is empirical will be clear from the methods and results section of the paper. Also, papers which compare empirical valuation studies on a specific topic, but do not present the original valuation results, need to be removed.

4. 0.3 - Is the paper presenting original results, based on measurements/observations/descriptions of nature or human-nature links? *

Mark only one oval.

- yes *Skip to question 5*
- No *Skip to section 7 (Out of scope / Crucial unclarity)*
- unclear *Skip to section 7 (Out of scope / Crucial unclarity)*

Applied context?

Our review focuses on applications in applied, real world contexts. Purely philosophical papers are to be removed. This 'decision making' context however is very broad: from assessing biodiversity, to comparing development scenarios' impact or to understanding people's diverse perspectives towards nature. The 'applied' justification is often found in intro and discussion sections.

5. 0.4 - Is the valuation presented in the paper performed in a real life context (by assessing nature itself / comparing alternatives / understanding people's perspectives towards nature?) *

Mark only one oval.

- yes
- No *Skip to section 7 (Out of scope / Crucial unclarity)*
- unclear *Skip to section 7 (Out of scope / Crucial unclarity)*

Number of applications

Some papers present several methodological approaches, location case studies, moments in time,... If these 'cases' are really separate 'applications', we need to score each one of them separately.

This information can be found in material and methods and results presentation:

We want to score any 'CASE' (methods/locations/moments/...) with SUFFICIENT UNIQUE INFORMATION as a separate APPLICATION.

A few definitions:

AN APPLICATION: an explicit valuation, applied in a concrete context (a certain place, time, distinct method/approach). However, an application might still use a combination of methods, or do valuations at different locations or times.

A 'MAIN' METHOD: a valuation method which provides the 'final' valuation results, which is separately described, and for which separate results are presented centrally in this paper. (Supporting / additional / 'mentioned in passing' methods which provide input to a main method can be added in a later stage!)

'SUFFICIENT' INFORMATION: When a 'case' (main method / location /...) contains descriptions which allow you to provide scores for most the 8 topics: (method use, application context, application descriptors, reliability, IPLMLC, wellbeing, ecological sustainability, justice).

'UNIQUE' INFORMATION: When a 'case' (main method / location /...) would generate unique scores on one of the topics, they are to be scored separately. If cases would score identically over all topics, they can be considered as one case (or be scored identically, but that's just more work)

!! Please note the number of applications down on a piece of paper: all review questions have to be filled in for every separate application, and you don't want to get lost !! eg. if there are three applications in paper 1312, note down: "paper nr 1312 - application A: Belgium; B: Netherlands; C: Denmark"

6. 0.5 - Does the paper represent several cases which can be scored as separate applications? *

Mark only one oval.

ONE application: Application with single main method, location, time,..

ONE application: Different main methods / locations / times / groups; BUT each has identical or insufficient information to score separately.

UNCLEAR: Different main methods / locations / times / groups AND goal is to combine results to a central valuation.

Skip to section 7 (Out of scope / Crucial unclarity)

SEVERAL applications: Different main methods / locations / times / groups, with sufficient information to score separately.

Application names

7. 0.6 - How many separate applications are presented in the paper? *

- 8. 0.7 - please provide short names for the applications. Be tidy: Letter : name ; [example: "A: Belgium; B: Denmark; C: Mexico. Use ";" to separate applications, and ":" to separate letter:name. Use CLEAR and SENSIBLE names which you will reuse in the next survey and allow finding it in the paper. *

Skip to question 9

Out of scope /
Crucial
unclarity

You have now removed a paper from the application review and sent it off to the chapter team to check. No worries, go to the next paper!

End of STEP 2 - paper
screening

Well done! Just one confidence question and then ... moving on. 8 more topics to go.

- 9. 0.8 - How sure do you feel about your scores for this step? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very sure	<input type="radio"/>	very unsure				

- 10. 0.9 - provide description to explain why, if you score 4 or 5.

Google Forms